

Between Inclusion and Exclusion: Data-Driven Keyword Generation for Machine-Readable Egodocuments

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With the large increase in digitisation, as well as machine-readability of documents, historians are able to browse through historical collections in new ways. Although for long the archivist remained in the background as a ‘neutral processor of the archive’, the steps taken both in analog and digital archival processes influence how, as well as which documents are accessed by historians. This workshop contribution discusses both manual and automated archival description in the form of keywords, in order to demonstrate how data-driven methods may be employed for further contextualization of documents.

As is the case for many historical archival institutions, the NIOD Institute for War, Holocaust and Genocide Studies holds a large variety of personal collections. These collections, which contain personal testimonies of wartime in the form of letters, diaries, or photographs, are the result of donations of private entities in society who have kept inherited documents from family members in their homes. After these documents make the transfer from attics or

basements to the repositories of archival institutions at a certain point in time, they pass through the hands of archivists in order to fit into the classification system of the archival organization.

In order to allow historians to access a large amount of private collections, archival institutes can organize their archives on an overarching thematic basis. The way archival catalogs are organized largely impacts the way historians find materials in archives.¹ Thematic finding aids such as keywords allow historical researchers to break through the original structure of an archive in order to find materials that are relevant for their research.² Rather than searching through each individual donation as a fonds, this allows users to search on the basis of certain themes, locations or timeframes. An example of such a collection is the NIOD-collection 247 *Correspondentie*, which consists of digitized letters from the WWII-period in the Netherlands, as well as the Independence War in Indonesia.³ This collection was, before being made full-text searchable, only accessible under hand-made exclusive categories such as ‘collaboration’, ‘children’, ‘liberation’ and ‘daily life’.

¹ Dunley, Richard, and Jo Pugh. “Do Archive Catalogues Make History?: Exploring Interactions Between Historians and Archives.” *Twentieth Century British History* 32, no. 4 (August 1, 2021): 581–607. <https://doi.org/10.1093/tcbh/hwab021>.

² Klein, Lauren F., Jacob Eisenstein, and Iris Sun. “Exploratory Thematic Analysis for Digitized Archival Collections.” *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* 30, no. 1 (October 5, 2015): 130–41. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqv052>.

³ “First-Hand Accounts of War.” 2024. NIOD. <https://www.niod.nl/en/projects/first-hand-accounts-war>.

These archival descriptions do not only work descriptive, but also have an epistemological function.⁴ Keywords are added by an archivist, who has to interpret the materials and the contextual information with which they were provided, to facilitate this. Although often-overlooked, the archivist can be seen as a subjective co-author of the archive rather than a neutral guardian.⁵ Given the interpretive nature of this process these descriptive keywords might, as many steps in the archival process, reflect values of the archivist. Next to this so-called ‘curatorial voice’ of the archivist,⁶ how materials are made accessible might follow historiographical trends, societal demands or might even have political dimensions.⁷

By generating keywords with data-driven methods such as TF-IDF, keywords can be extracted from literal text as written by the author, rather than from contextual information processed by the archivist. TF-IDF (short for term frequency-inverse document frequency) takes into account the frequency of a word in a certain document as well as in a whole corpus of

text. In doing so, it provides a method to determine the most distinctive words for a certain body of text in a transparent and replicable manner.

Similarly to manual description, data-driven keyword generation is based on a series of decisions.⁸ Due to its use of text-as-data, this method makes use of the language as used by the author rather than that created by the archivist to describe the materials. By creating a measure for the distinctiveness of words, this gives a different view of the themes and topics of historical egodocuments. Although there might also be themes that manifest themselves less in the material and can only be captured by close reading of the text, data-driven methods provide a view next to this through keywords based on the frequency of words.

Applying these methods requires collaboration between historians and archivists. Approaching materials in different ways contributes to better contextualization of these materials. In this way, historical researchers can also use these methods to analyze materials in ways that work beyond the curatorial voice of the archivist. As archival description influences how historians search and find materials, archival institutes can stimulate more diverse use of personal thematic collections by adding different layers of description. In this way, data-driven methods can contribute to highlighting a diverse set of voices from varied archival collections.

⁴ Rawson, K. J. “The Rhetorical Power of Archival Description: Classifying Images of Gender Transgression.” *Rhetoric Society Quarterly* 48, no. 4. (September 8, 2017): 327–51.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02773945.2017.1347951>.

⁵ Cook, Terry and Schwartz, Joan M. “Archives, Records and Power: From (Postmodern) Theory to (Archival) Practice.” *Archival Science*. no. 2, 2002, pp. 171-185.

⁶ Salway, Andrew, and Baker, James. “Investigating Curatorial Voice with Corpus Linguistic Techniques.” *Museum and Society* 18, no. 2 (July 4, 2020): 151–69. <https://doi.org/10.29311/mas.v18i2.3175>.

⁷ Zaagsma, Gerben. “Digital History and the Politics of Digitization.” *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* 38, no. 2 (September 16, 2022): 830–51. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lhc/fqac050>.

⁸ Steps in preprocessing data have an impact on the outcome of the analysis. See: Blaney, Jonathan, et. al. *Doing Digital History: A Beginner’s Guide to Working with Text as Data*. Manchester University Press, 2021.

Biography

Arvid de Raaij (1998) has a background in archival studies and is currently affiliated with the NIOD Institute for War-, Holocaust- and Genocide Studies in Amsterdam, where he works as a junior employee digital acquisition. Working on the intersection of history and archival studies, he is interested in the transformation of analog documents into the digital realm and investigates how users interact with different forms of digital archives. Focusing on natural language processing, he critically approaches various digital methods and how they can be used in order to make different aspects of the archival process more transparent.

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